

Quantum Max-Cut Classifier, A Quantum Artificial Intelligence Technique; Application in Cancer Diagnosis

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to create an intelligent classifier which separates cancer cells from healthy cells in the radiography image, efficiently. We first used a mathematical technique in "graph theory" called "Max-Cut". But complex images make the complexity of the classifying problem increased, and the efficiency of the output decreased. In order to speed up the process, we re-modelled the problem in a quantum computing framework, and adopted a quantum algorithm in order to perform some part of the calculations. A quantum optimization algorithm called "QAOA" was used in optimizing the objective function. The results were promising in two ways: First, the pixels of the image, captured from the biological tissue, do not need a "feature space", just the image itself. Second, for large scale problems, the speed up is proven for this algorithm.

Keywords:

Cancer Diagnosis, Quantum Computing, Quantum Artificial Intelligence, Quantum Max-Cut, Quantum Optimization

1 Introduction

Performing effective treatment in many diseases needs diagnosis at an early stage. Artificial intelligence and machine learning techniques demonstrates potentials in early cancer diagnosis [1, 2, 3]. Although some AI and ML techniques have shown that can equal the performance of expert readers [4], we believe such tools are just aids for physicians. Many machine learning algorithms have been developed and used in order to assist physicians encountering the illness. Image processing is a tool for this purpose. Identifying and classifying cancer cells are important measures before adopting treatment techniques such as radiotherapy[5, 6]. The machine learning classifier gets the image of the biological tissue and put it in a matrix and starts

processing it using some kind of ML techniques such as "Support Vector Machine", or "Artificial Neural Network" which usually need "feature space" of the pixels. That means an n-dimensional vector including n features of a pixel (cell) is needed for each pixel.

Maximum cut (Max-Cut) algorithm has the potential to identify and classify healthy and non-healthy cells with no need to any feature space[7]. They just need the difference between them (in this case, the color intensity) which is considered as weights between nodes (cells) of a graph.

We adopted the idea of classifying cells by Max-Cut algorithm using quantum computing techniques. Quantum computers provide scientists with speed up in running some algorithms including this one. Regarding the potential advances in quantum computing world, it is necessary and useful for cancer diagnosis to focus on this promising field.

1.1 Maximum-Cut Problem

A maximum cut is defined in "graph theory". It consists of some nodes (vertices) and some edges connecting them. The edges might be weighted. A cut on the edges of the graph, partitions the nodes into two subsets which are complementary. A maximum cut is such that the number of edges between two sets of nodes is as large as possible. The "max-cut problem" is finding such a separating cut.

Consider S and T are two complementary subsets of the vertices of a graph. The number of edges between these subsets need to be as large as possible. On the other word, we need a bipartite graph with as many edges as possible. We are also interested in weighted max-cut, where each edge has weight which is a real number. In this case the objective is not to maximize the number of the edges but to maximize the total weight of the edges between S and T.

Consider G as a graph. If one wants to determine whether there is a cut of size at least k in G where k is an integer, they have shown that this problem is to be NP-complete[8][9].

So, the Maximum-Cut Problem is modelled mathematically as:

Consider $G = (V, E, w)$ be an undirected graph with n nodes where $V = |V| = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Each edge E has a weight w where $w_{ij} > 0$, $w_{ij} = w_{ji}$ for $(i, j) \in E$. This is a weighted adjacency matrix of this graph and is symmetric. If one wants to divide the nodes set V into two subsets they would need an imaginary cut over some or all edges. In order to optimize the weighted Max-Cut problem the objective function is the sum of weights of edges connecting points in the two subsets which are divided by the optimized cut. The usual formulation is

$$\max \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} \frac{1 - x_i x_j}{2}.$$

For binary problems such as this study which aim at classifying (separating) items (cells) into 2 classes, each node x_i can get the values 0 or 1, cancer or healthy, $x_i \in \{0, 1\}$. So the objective function to be maximized is:

$$C = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_{i,j} x_i (1 - x_j). \quad (1)$$

Given a graph G, find a maximum cut is known to be NP-Hard. When the number of pixels increases, the complexity of calculation grows exponentially, which leads to decrease in the efficiency of the algorithm. What matters to our case is it really affects the patient's health situation. To optimize the Max-Cut problem we need efficient optimization algorithms.

1.2 Mathematical Optimization

The selection of a best solution, with regard to some criterion, from some set of available alternative elements is a usual problem in real applications. Such problems are called "mathematical optimization". The problem formulation consists of maximizing or minimizing a real function by systematically choosing input values from within an allowed set and computing the value of the function.

"Discrete optimization" is a branch of optimization in which some or all of the variables used in a discrete optimization problem are restricted to be discrete variables. A subfield of mathematical optimization that consists of finding an optimal object from a "finite" set of objects is called "combinatorial optimization". In many such problems, exhaustive search is not tractable, and so approximation algorithms must be used instead.

A wide class of optimization problems cannot be solved exactly in polynomial time. Approximation algorithms are efficient algorithms that find approximate solutions to optimization problems. Such methods help us to understand how closely it is possible to approximate optimal solutions to such problems in polynomial time.

1.3 Max-Cut as a Binary Classifier in Machine Learning

Max-Cut algorithm has already been studied and used as machine learning technique for classifying and clustering[7]. Treating its nodes as features and its edges as distances, the max-cut algorithm divides a graph in two well-separated subsets.

Consider the nodes of a bipartite graph as features and its edges as distances. The max cut algorithm divides a graph in two subsets which could be used as a binary classifier. The distances between vertices are sufficient for this purpose. So, this does not require a feature space.[10]

1.4 Quantum Computing

Unlike classical (digital) computer, A quantum computer takes advantage of quantum mechanical properties (such as superposition and entanglement) which is different from Newtonian mechanics. The basic unit of information and processing is the qubit (quantum bit). Unlike a classical bit, a qubit can exist in a superposition of its two "basis" states that means in both states simultaneously. By measuring a qubit, it collapses into 0 or 1. If a quantum computer manipulates the qubit in a particular way, the effects can amplify the desired measurement results. We can design a quantum algorithm to make a quantum computer perform calculations efficiently and quickly.

1.5 Quantum Optimization

Quantum optimization algorithms are quantum algorithms that are used to solve optimization problems[11]. As the complexity and amount of data involved in problems rise, more efficient ways of solving optimization problems are needed. Quantum computing provides the opportunity to solve some problems that are unfeasible on usual classical computers, or, at least provide us with a considerable speed up.

Some kinds of quantum algorithms for optimization are in the field of combinatorics. The combinatorial optimization problems try to find an optimal solution among finite set of feasible solutions. That is maximization of an objective function which is a sum of "Boolean functions" which are as $C : \{0, 1\}^n \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$. The input of a Boolean function is the n -string $z = z_1 z_2 \dots z_n$. The output is a one-bit data (0 or 1). The combinatorial optimization problem of n -bit string z maximizes the function

$$C(z) = \sum_{\alpha=1}^m C(z)$$

Now we are at a point to model a scan image of a context to a graph, and solve the optimization problem of the Max-Cut problem using quantum algorithms.

2 Materials and Methods

The hypothesis for the research is:

A quantum Max-Cut algorithm has the ability to separate cancer cells from healthy cells in a MRI image.

This is a prospective study.

2.1 Modeling the Quantum Max-Cut Problem

First of all, imagine the biological tissue is been scanned and a small part of it including 9 biological cells is chosen. Then each cell is allocated to each

pixel. Pixels have color intensity. Cancer cells have higher color intensity rather than healthy ones due to their larger nucleus (membrane).

Here we map the image into a 3*3 tabular, see table 1:

C	H	H
C	C	H
C	H	H

Table 1: Context Image, 9 Pixels, C for cancer cells and H for Healthy cells

The aim is to separate cancer cells from healthy ones for treatment purposes, such as radiotherapy.

In order to model the image, mathematically, first we define n vertices, and weights between them. Difference between color intensity of the neighbouring nodes is defined as the weight of the edge between them. Then each vertex is allocated to a qubit on the real quantum computer. We have run the algorithm on a quantum simulator first which is enough for research and experimental purposes. In our case the network graph is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Network Graph with 9 nodes

At this stage the weight matrix is calculated. Since the problem has n variables, we got 2^n combinations.

Before we begin with the quantum computing technique, we ran the model on a classical computer in order to compare the results of corresponding quantum algorithm later.

For next step, we map the problem to the objective function (Ising) which is described in section 2.4.

2.2 Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm (QAOA)

Consider an objective function $C(z)$ consisting variables $z_j = z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n$, where each z_j has two possible values; $z_j \in \{-1, +1\}$ by convention. The goal of QAOA is to produce an assignment of the z_j that gives a relatively low (but not the lowest) value of $C(z)$. That's why they have chosen the name "Approximate".

The QAOA algorithm acts on n qubits. Each qubit represents one of the variables in the objective function. The 2^n possible assignments of the z_j variables results in the 2^n states of the computational basis. The value of z_j corresponds to the measurement outcome of the Pauli- Z operator on the j th qubit.

The qubits are initialized in the $|0\rangle$ state. Then the $H^{\otimes n}$, the Hadamard operator is imposed on each qubit. By this, all bitstrings have equal superpositions. That means an equal superposition of all possible z assignments:

$$H^{\otimes n}|0^n\rangle = \frac{1}{2^{n/2}} \sum_{x \in \{0,1\}^n} |x\rangle.$$

Now we affect the amplitudes so that those with small $C(z)$ values grow while those with large $C(z)$ values shrink. At the end of procedure, we measure the qubits we will expect to find a bitstring with a small value of $C(z)$.

Consider the following unitary operator:

$$U(\gamma, C) = e^{i\pi\gamma C(Z)/2}.$$

The parameter γ is a variational parameter, adjusting its value to produce the best possible result. The objective function C is to be minimized. The notation $C(Z)$ means we need to plug in the Pauli- Z operator for each qubit in place of the argument z .

Now we act with $U(C, \gamma)$. The result is a sum over all possible bit-strings, and, of course the coefficients are complex phases which depend on C . There is still an equal probability to measure any particular string.

Now we act with the unitary operator

$$U(\beta, B) = e^{i\pi\beta B/2}, \quad B = \sum_{j=1}^n X_j,$$

where β is a variational parameter. The Pauli- X operators on each qubit commute with each other, So we have

$$U(\beta, B) = \prod_{j=1}^n e^{i\pi\beta X_j/2}.$$

This is a rotation of each qubit around the X -axis on the Bloch sphere by an amount determined by β . This operation is not diagonal in the computational basis. The resulting state will not be an equal superposition over all bitstrings. There will be some constructive and destructive interference. This process leads to states corresponding to small values of C . The $U(\beta, B)$ is a "mixing" operation.

The circuit repeats the previous two steps a total of $p \geq 1$ times. The choice

of p is up to the researcher who also choose the parameters γ and β independently at each step. So, at the the of the circuit, the state of the qubits is

$$|\gamma, \beta\rangle = U(\beta_p, B)U(\gamma_p, C) \cdots \\ U(\beta_1, B)U(\gamma_1, C)H^{\otimes n}|0^n\rangle.$$

We suppose to choose γ and β so that the expectation value

$$F(\gamma, \beta) = \langle \gamma, \beta | C(Z) | \gamma, \beta \rangle \quad (2)$$

is minimized. So, the act of measuring the state $|\gamma, \beta\rangle$ in the computational basis provides us with a good candidate bitstring for the minimum of $C(z)$. The QAOA algorithm so requires the following steps:

1. Create the $U(\gamma, C)$ operation.
2. Create a quantum circuit alternating $U(\gamma, C)$ and $U(\beta, B)$ operations as many times as desired.
3. Find the optimal value of the variational parameters in the circuit.
4. Measure the output of our circuit.

2.3 Quantum Max-Cut

The problem with classical computers in algorithms like "Max-Cut" is that when the nodes (cells/pixels) and the relationship (the number of edges and corresponding weights) increases, the calculation complexity increases exponentially. That's why we have chosen quantum computing for this purpose.

In order to maximize the objective function by a quantum computer one should map the problem on Ising Hamiltonian. To do so x_i need to be transformed to $(1 - Z_i)/2$, where Z_i is the Pauli matrix (operator) that has eigenvalues $+1$ and -1 . So the objective function transforms to:

$$C(\mathbf{Z}) = \sum_{i,j} w_{i,j} \left(\frac{1 - z_i}{2} \right) \left(\frac{1 - z_j}{2} \right) \\ = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{w_{ij}}{4} (1 - Z_i) (1 + Z_j) \\ = -\frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{i<j} w_{ij} Z_i Z_j \right) + \sum_{i<j} w_{ij}/2 \quad (3)$$

The second term on the right-hand side of the cost function 3 is a constant number. So, the equivalent problem is minimizing the Ising Hamiltonian equation:

$$H = \sum_{i<j} w_{ij} Z_i Z_j \quad (4)$$

on the other word:

$$\text{Maximize } C(z) \approx \text{Minimize } H$$

2.4 Using QAOA in Solving Quantum Max-Cut

The aim is to minimize the Ising Hamiltonian. We choose the depth of the quantum circuit m . Considering trial wavefunction $|\psi(\theta)\rangle$ with θ as a set of control parameters, we make a quantum circuit by C-phase gates and single-qubit Y rotations. Then we calculate the objective function C using the parameters θ . For this, we need to sample the outcome of the circuit in the Z-basis and add the expectation values of the Ising term together:

$$\begin{aligned} C(\theta) &= \langle \psi(\theta) | H | \psi(\theta) \rangle \\ &= \sum_{i < j} w_{ij} \langle \psi(\theta) | Z_i Z_j | \psi(\theta) \rangle \end{aligned}$$

We also need to choose a classical optimizer and then estimate different points around θ . By using a classical optimizer, we are able to choose a new set of control parameters. This process continues until the objective function $C(\theta)$ is the minimum value close enough to the solution θ^* . The last θ is used to generate a set of samples which are the last set and for all i are obtained from the distribution $|\langle z_i | \psi(\theta) \rangle|^2$. The answer is ready.

3 Results

We have run the algorithm on a quantum simulator, and on a real quantum computer as well. The result is shown in figure 2

Figure 2: Quantum Max-Cut Output

We can observe the nodes are well separated into two sections, exactly in accordance with the data in the table 1. The red nodes represent cancer cells. The cell number, location and connection to other cells is completely according to the image scanned from the real tissue (table). That means

the algorithm has separated cancer cells from the healthy ones efficiently. So, the hypothesis is true.

The reason for the low dimension of the instance (3*3) is the need for simulating in a visual diagram. The algorithm performs well with more cells (nodes). In fact, it is the reason for using quantum approach.

4 Discussion

4.1 Method Analysis

The algorithm of our method is as follows:

Inputs: number of the nodes of the network, the edge weights.

Output: maximized total wights of edges between two sections.

1. define the number of variables as nodes
2. investigate if there are edges between every two nodes.
3. define the weights between nodes.
4. prepare the formulation for objective function to be maximized.
5. Map the model to an Ising Hamiltonian to be minimized.

We may compare our "Quantum Max-Cut" classifier with some imaginary "SVM" classifiers in figure 3, where the SVM classifiers can't separate nodes efficiently. If one uses SVM, some healthy nodes could be damaged during the radiotherapy treatment, or, some cancer cells would be left intact.

Figure 3: Comparing the imaginary quantum Max-Cut curve (yellow curve) with some imaginary SVMs (black lines)

We used a simple image with 9 pixels which are mapped into a graph with 9 vertices. The problem can be solved for real $x*y$ pixel images as well.

4.2 Optimization Analysis

The algorithm for optimization task is:

1. Choose the depth of the quantum circuit.
2. Choose a set of controls θ and then define a function $|\psi(\theta)\rangle$
3. Calculate the $C(\theta) = \langle\psi(\theta)|H|\psi(\theta)\rangle$
4. Choose a new set of controls using a classical computer.
5. Continue the process until you reach a minimum.
6. Use the last θ to obtain the final set of samples which is the target solution.

The algorithm depends on an integer $p \geq 1$. The quality of the approximation improves as p is increased[12]. We aim to find a string z for which $C(z)$ is close to the global maximum. To do so the $F(\gamma, \beta) = \langle\gamma, \beta|C(Z)|\gamma, \beta\rangle$ needs to be minimized. We use a classical computer simultaneously to obtain the best set of angles which is used again and again in the computing process.

The relative speed-up of the QAOA is an open research question. It has a better approximation ratio than any known polynomial time classical algorithm for a certain problem[12]. Quantum supremacy with a QAOA circuit is discussed in a paper[13] that explains an example that would require at least one century to be simulated using a classical simulation algorithm running on state-of-the-art supercomputers. This proves the quantum computational supremacy over classical one, indeed.

4.3 Discussion

Although exponential speedup in using quantum computers compared to the best classical algorithms is not guaranteed yet, it is worth to design and implement heuristic approaches which could probably make some problem instances run faster. By the way, we are waiting for improvements in architecture of quantum devices. That will definitely facilitate current quantum algorithms by decreasing noises.

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